

Time economic innovative pedagogies in chemical science – A review article

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Abstract : In this review article, text based learning approaches have been highlighted by innovative and time economic way to enhance interest of students' who belong to paranoia zone in chemical science. In this pedagogical survey, we have tried to hub fifteen (15) time economic pedagogies by including thirty six (36) new formulae in the field of chemical education. This review explores the results and gives implications for context based teaching, learning and assessment.

Keywords : General public, high school, graduate student, chemical education research, organic and inorganic chemistry, problem solving, M.O. theory, alkenes, alkynes, aromatic compounds.

Introduction

The conventional methods¹⁻¹³ for determination of hybridization state of simple molecules or ions including heterocyclic compounds, bond order for diatomic homo and hetero nuclear molecules or ions having (1-20)e⁻s using M.O.T., bond-order of oxide based acid radicals, prediction of spin state using spin multiplicity value, aromatic and anti-aromatic behavior of organic compounds, evaluation of magnetic behaviour of homo and hetero nuclear diatomic molecules or ions having (1-20)e⁻s without M.O.T., calculation of the number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds in aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons and alkynes etc. is time consuming. Keeping this in mind, in this survey, we have introduced some innovative methods¹⁴⁻²⁴ to make chemistry metabolic, time economic and interesting. Here, we have tried to discuss them abruptly.

Innovative time economic pedagogies :

1. Innovative thinking on the prediction of hybridization state of simple molecules or ions :

Professor Linus Pauling (1931) first developed the hybridization state theory in order to explain the structure of molecules such as methane (CH_4). This concept was developed for simple chemical systems but this one applied more widely later on and from today's point of view it is considered an operative empirical for excusing the structures of organic and inorganic compounds along with their related problems.

1.1. Prediction of sp , sp^2 , sp^3 hybridization state :

We know, hybridization is nothing but the mixing of orbital's in different ratio to form some newly synthesized orbitals called hybrid orbitals. The mixing pattern is as follows :

$s + p$ (1 : 1) - sp hybrid orbital;

$s + p$ (1 : 2) - sp^2 hybrid orbital; $s + p$ (1 : 3) - sp^3 hybrid orbital

Formula used for the determination of sp , sp^2 and sp^3 hybridization state :

Power on the hybridization state of the central atom =

(Total no. of σ bonds around each central atom - 1)

All single (-) bonds are σ bond, in double bond (=) there is one σ and 1π , in triple bond (\equiv) there is one σ and 2π . In addition to these each lone pair (LP) and co-ordinate bond can be treated as one σ bond subsequently.

e.g. :

(a) In NH_3 : central atom N is surrounded by three N-H single bonds i.e. three sigma (σ) bonds and one lone pair (LP) i.e. one additional σ bond. So, in NH_3 there is a total of four σ bonds [3 bond pairs (BPs) + 1 lone pair (LP)] around central atom N. Therefore, in this case power of the hybridization state of N = $4-1 = 3$ i.e. hybridization state = sp^3 .

(b) In H_2O : central atom O is surrounded by two O-H single bonds i.e. two sigma (σ) bonds and two lone pairs i.e. two additional σ bonds. So, altogether in H_2O there are four σ bonds (2 bond pairs + 2 lone pairs) around central atom O, so, in this case power of the hybridization state of O = $4-1 = 3$ i.e. hybridization state of O in $\text{H}_2\text{O} = sp^3$.

(c) In H_3BO_3 : B has 3σ bonds (3BPs but no LPs) and oxygen has 4σ bonds (2BPs and 2LPs) so, in this case power of the hybridization state of B = $3-1 = 2$ i.e. B is sp^2 hybridized in H_3BO_3 . On the other hand, power of the hybridization state of O = $4-1 = 3$ i.e. hybridization state of O in H_3BO_3 is sp^3 .

(d) In I-Cl : I and Cl both have 4σ bonds and 3LPs, so, in this case power of the hybridization state of both I and Cl = $4-1 = 3$ i.e. hybridization state of I and Cl both are sp^3 .

(e) In $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}_2$: each carbon is attached with 2 C-H single bonds (2σ bonds) and one C=C bond (1σ bond), so, altogether there are 3 sigma bonds. So, in this case, power of the hybridization state of both C = $3-1 = 2$ i.e. hybridization state of both C's are sp^2 .

1.2. Prediction of sp^3d , sp^3d^2 , sp^3d^3 hybridization state :

In case of sp^3d , sp^3d^2 and sp^3d^3 hybridization state there is a common term sp^3 for which 4 sigma bonds are responsible. So, in addition to 4 sigma bonds, for each additional sigma, added one d orbital gradually as follows :

$$5\sigma \text{ bonds} = 4\sigma \text{ bonds} + 1 \text{ additional } \sigma \text{ bond} = sp^3d \text{ hybridization}$$

$$6\sigma \text{ bonds} = 4\sigma \text{ bonds} + 2 \text{ additional } \sigma \text{ bonds} = sp^3d^2 \text{ hybridization}$$

$$7\sigma \text{ bonds} = 4\sigma \text{ bonds} + 3 \text{ additional } \sigma \text{ bonds} = sp^3d^3 \text{ hybridization}$$

e.g. :

(a) IF_4^- :

I has 7 e^- s in its outermost shell, so, in this case, subtract one e^- from 7 i.e. $7-1 = 6$. So, out of 6 electrons, 4 electrons form 4 I-F bonds i.e. 4 sigma bonds and there is one LP. So, altogether there are 5 σ bonds. So, 5 σ bonds = 4 σ bonds + 1 additional σ bond = sp^3d hybridization.

(b) **IF₇**: 7 I-F single bonds i.e. 7 σ bonds = 4 σ bonds + 3 additional σ bonds = sp^3d^3 hybridization.

(c) **ICl₂⁻**: I has 7 e^- s in its outermost shell, so, in this case, add one e^- with 7 (overall charge on the compound) i.e. $07 + 1 = 08$. So, out of 08 electrons, 02 electrons form 02 I-Cl bonds i.e. 02 sigma bonds and there is 03 LPs. So, altogether there are 05 σ bonds. So, σ bonds = 04 σ bonds + 01 additional σ bond = sp^3d hybridization.

(d) **XeF₄**:

Xe, an inert gas, consider 8 e^- s in its outermost shell, 04 of which form 04 Xe-F sigma bonds and there is two LPs, i.e. altogether there is 06 σ bonds = 04 σ bonds + 02 additional σ bonds = sp^3d^2 hybridization.

In case of determination of the hybridization state by using the above method, one must have a clear idea about the outermost electrons of different family members in the periodic table as follows :

Family	Outermost electrons
Nitrogen family	05
Oxygen family	06
Halogen family	07
Inert gas family	08

In case of cationic species you must remove requisite electron/electrons from the outermost orbit of the central atom and incase of anionic species you must add requisite electron with the outermost electrons of the central atom. Examples have been explored in Table 1.

Table 1. Total number of σ bonds and hybridization state

Total number of sigma (σ) bonds	Nature of hybridization state	Examples
2	sp	BeCl ₂ , HgCl ₂ , C ₂ H ₂ , CO ₂ , CO, CdCl ₂ , ZnCl ₂ etc.
3	sp ²	BCl ₃ , AlCl ₃ , C ₂ H ₄ , C ₆ H ₆ , SO ₂ , SO ₃ , HNO ₃ , H ₂ CO ₃ , SnCl ₂ , PbCl ₂ etc.
4	sp ³	NH ₄ ⁺ , BF ₄ ⁻ , H ₂ SO ₄ , HClO ₄ , PCl ₃ , NCl ₃ , AsCl ₃ , HClO ₃ , ICl ₂ ⁺ , OF ₂ , HClO ₂ , SCl ₂ , HClO, ICl, XeO ₃ etc.
5	sp ³ d	PCl ₅ , SbCl ₅ , SF ₄ , ClF ₃ , BrF ₃ , XeF ₂ , ICl ₂ ⁻ etc.
6	sp ³ d ²	SF ₆ , AlF ₆ ³⁻ , SiF ₆ ²⁻ , PF ₆ ⁻ , IF ₅ , BrF ₅ , XeOF ₄ , XeF ₄ , BrF ₄ ⁻ , ICl ₄ ⁻ etc.
7	sp ³ d ³	IF ₇ , XeF ₆ etc.

1.3. Prediction of hybridization state of hetero atom in heterocyclic compounds :

In this case, state of s-p hybridization of hetero atoms in heterocyclic compounds have been empirically calculated from the number of bonds and delocalized lone pair of electrons associated with it in the following way :

$$\text{Total power on hybridization state (X)} = \text{TNBS} + \text{DLP}$$

where, TNBS = total number of bonds directly attached with hetero atom excluding H bond if any attached with hetero atom and DLP = delocalized lone pair electrons through resonance.

- For sp; power on s = 1 and power on p = 1, hence total power = (1+1) = 2
- For sp²; power on s = 1 and power on p = 2, hence total power = (1+2) = 3
- For sp³; power on s = 1 and power on p = 3, hence total power = (1+3) = 4

Examples have been illustrated in Table 2.

2. New dimension for the prediction of bond-order :

Bond-order usually predicted from the Molecular Orbital Theory. Molecular Orbital Theory (M.O.T.) was first proposed by Friedrich Hund and Robert Mulliken in 1933. They developed an approach to covalent bond

Table 2. Hybridization state of hetero atoms in some heterocyclic compounds

Heterocyclic compounds	TNBS (Total number of bonds around hetero atom excluding H bond)	DLP (Delocalized lone pair of e ⁻ s)	Total power (X) = TNBS+DLP	Hybridization state
 Pyrrole	2	1	3	sp ²
 Furan	2	1	3	sp ²
		(Out of two lone pair of electrons, one can take part in delocalization at a time)		
 Thiophene	2	1	3	sp ²
		(Out of two lone pair of electrons, one can take part in delocalization at a time)		
 Pyridine	3	0	3	sp ²
		(Lone pair on nitrogen does not undergo delocalization)		

Table 1 (contd.)

	2	1	3	sp^2
Indole				
	3	0	3	sp^2
Quinoline		(Lone pair on nitrogen does not undergo delocalization)		

formation which is based upon the effects of the various electron fields upon each other and which employs molecular orbital rather than atomic orbital. Each such orbital characterizing the molecule as a whole is described by a definite combination of quantum numbers and possesses relative energy value.

2.1. For homo and hetero nuclear diatomic molecules or ions having (1-20)e⁻s :

Graphical representation of B.O. with number of electrons :

Fig. 1. B.O. vs number of electrons.

The graphical representation presented in Fig. 1 shows that bond-order gradually increases to 1 in the range (0-2) electrons then falls to zero in the range (2-4) electrons then it further rises to 1 for (4-6) electrons and once

again falls to zero for (6-8) electrons then again rises to 3 in the range (8-14) electrons and then finally falls to zero for (14-20) electrons. For total no. of electrons 2, 6 and 14, we may use multiple formulae, because they fall in the overlapping region in which they intersect with each other.

First of all we classify the molecules or ions into the following four (4) types based on total number of electrons present in them.

(i) Molecules and ions having total no. of electrons within the range (1-2) :

In such case Bond order = $n/2$ [where n = total no. of electrons] e.g. H_2 (Total $e^-s = 2$), therefore B.O. = $n/2 = 2/2 = 1$.

(ii) Molecules and ions having total no. of electrons within the range (2-6) :

In such case Bond order = $I4-nI/2$ [where n = total no. of electrons, 'I' indicates Mod function i.e. the value of bond order is always positive].

e.g. $L_2^+(5e^-s)$ therefore B.O. = $I4-5I/2 = 1/2 = 0.5$.

(iii) Molecules and ions having total no. of electrons within the range (6-14) :

In such case Bond order = $I8-nI/2$

e.g. CO (Total $e^-s = 6+8=14$), therefore B.O. = $I8-14I/2 = 3$.

(iv) Molecules and ions having total no. of electrons within the range (14-20) :

In such case Bond order = $(20-n)/2$ [where n = total no. of electrons] e.g. NO (Total $e^-s = 15$), therefore B.O. = $20-15/2 = 2.5$.

Bond order prediction with examples have been represented in Table 3.

2.2. Innovative way for the prediction of bond order in case of oxide based acid radicals :

In case of oxide based acid radicals :

Bond order (B.O.) = Oxidation number of the peripheral atom + (charge on acid radical/total number of peripheral atoms).

e.g. :

ClO_4^- : (Oxidation number of one peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge

Table 3. Bond order values for homo and hetero nuclear diatomic species having (1–20)e⁻s

Species (Molecules or ions)	Total number of e ⁻ s (n)	Bond order (B.O.)
Bond-order values for the species having (1–2)e ⁻ s; Bond order = n/2		
H ₂ ⁺	1	0.5
H ₂ , He ₂ ²⁺	2	1
Bond-order values for the species having (2–6)e ⁻ s; Bond order = I4–nI/2		
H ₂ ⁻ , He ₂ ⁺	3	0.5
He ₂	4	0
Li ₂ ⁺ , He ₂ ⁻	5	0.5
Li ₂ , He ₂ ²⁻ , Be ₂ ²⁺	6	1
Bond-order values for the species having (6–14)e ⁻ s; Bond order = I8–nI/2		
Be ₂ ⁺ , Li ₂ ⁻	7	0.5
Be ₂ , Li ₂ ²⁻	8	0
Be ₂ ⁻ , B ₂ ⁺	9	0.5
B ₂ , Be ₂ ²⁻ , HF	10	1
B ₂ ⁻ , C ₂ ⁺	11	1.5
C ₂ , B ₂ ²⁻ , N ₂ ²⁺ , CN ⁺	12	2
C ₂ ⁻ , N ₂ ⁺	13	2.5
N ₂ , CO, NO ⁺ , C ₂ ²⁻ , CN ⁻ , O ₂ ²⁺	14	3
Bond-order values for the species having (14–20)e ⁻ s; Bond order = (20–n)/2		
N ₂ ⁻ , NO, O ₂ ⁺	15	2.5
NO ⁻ , O ₂	16	2
O ₂ ⁻	17	1.5
F ₂ , O ₂ ²⁻ , HCl	18	1
F ₂ ⁻	19	0.5
Ne ₂	20	0

on acid radical = -1, total number of peripheral atoms = 04), therefore B.O. = 2 + (-1/4) = 1.75.

ClO₃⁻ : (Oxidation number of one peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -1, total number of peripheral atoms = 03), therefore B.O. = 2 + (-1/3) = 1.66.

ClO₂⁻ : (Oxidation number of one peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -1, total number of peripheral atoms = 02), therefore B.O. = 2 + (-1/2) = 1.5.

AsO_4^{3-} : (Oxidation number of one peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -3, total number of peripheral atoms = 04), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-3/4) = 1.25$.

AsO_3^{3-} : (Oxidation number of one peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -3, total number of peripheral atoms = 03), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-3/3) = 1.0$.

SO_4^{2-} : (Oxidation number of peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -2, number of peripheral atoms = 04), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-2/4) = 1.5$.

SO_3^{2-} : (Oxidation number of peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -2, number of peripheral atoms = 03), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-2/3) = 1.33$.

PO_4^{3-} : (Oxidation number of peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -3, number of peripheral atoms = 04), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-3/4) = 1.25$.

BO_3^{3-} : (Oxidation number of peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -3, number of peripheral atoms = 03), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-3/3) = 1$.

CO_3^{2-} : (Oxidation number of peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -2, number of peripheral atoms = 03), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-2/3) = 1.33$.

SiO_4^{4-} : (Oxidation number of peripheral atom oxygen = 2, charge on acid radical = -4, number of peripheral atoms = 04), therefore B.O. = $2 + (-4/4) = 1$.

Relation of Bond order with Bond length, Bond strength, Bond energy, Thermal stability and Reactivity :

B.O. \propto 1/Bond length or Bond distance; B.O. \propto Bond strength; B.O. \propto Bond energy; B.O. \propto Thermal stability; B.O. \propto 1/Reactivity

Correlation among/between literature values of bond-distances of some oxide based acid radicals with their predicted bond order values :

Literature values of the Cl-O average bond lengths in ClO_4^- , ClO_3^- and ClO_2^- ; As-O bond lengths in AsO_4^{3-} and AsO_3^{3-} with respect to their bond

order values suggest that with increasing bond-order M-O bond length (where M = Cl, As etc.) decreases which is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Correlation of some bond-distances with their predicted bond order values

Oxide based acid radicals	Bond-order values	Avg. M-O bond-distances as per literature (Å)	Remarks
ClO_4^-	1.75	1.50	
ClO_3^-	1.6	1.57	Increasing bond-order decreases bond length
ClO_2^-	1.5	1.64	
AsO_4^{3-}	1.25	1.75	
AsO_3^{3-}	1.0	1.77	

3. New dimension on the prediction of magnetic behavior of homo and hetero nuclear diatomic species (molecules or ions) :

The present study involves three new formulae by just manipulating the number of unpaired electrons (n) using Mod function (based on Applied Mathematics) and by means of these n values one can easily stumble the magnetic moment values in Bohr-Magneton using spin only formula $\mu_s = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$ B.M., where B.M. = Bohr-Magneton = unit of magnetic moment, n = number of unpaired electrons.

First of all we classify the molecules or ions depending on the total number of electrons present in them in the following three (03) sets.

Set-1 : Molecules or ions having (1-3)e⁻s, (3-5)e⁻s, (5-7)e⁻s, (7-10)e⁻s, (13-16)e⁻s

Set-2 : Molecules or ions having (10-13)e⁻s and (16-19)e⁻s

Set-3 : Molecules or ions having 20e⁻s

Then for different set we have to use three different formulae to calculate the number of unpaired electrons which have been presented in Table 5 and thus magnetic moment (μ_s in B.M.) can be evaluated in the following way :

3.1. F-1 (For Set-I) – for the determination of number of unpaired electrons (n) of molecules or ions having total number of electrons (1-3), (3-5), (5-7), (7-10) and (13-16)e⁻s :

In this case, the number of unpaired electrons $n = [I(\text{ND-total } e^-)I]$.

Here, ND = next digit i.e. digit next to minimum digit and 'I I' indicates Mod function. e.g. Molecules or ions having (1-3)e⁻s, in this case ND = 2 because here minimum digit is 1. e.g. He₂⁺(3e⁻s), the total number of electrons will be 3, ND = 2, hence, unpaired electron n = I(ND-total e⁻s)I = I(2-3)I = 1. Hence, magnetic moment $\mu_s = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$ B.M. = $\sqrt{1(1+2)}$ B.M. = $\sqrt{3}$ B.M. = 1.73 B.M.

For the molecules or ions containing (3-5)e⁻s, (5-7)e⁻s, (7-10)e⁻s and (13-16)e⁻s the ND value will be 4, 6, 8 and 14 respectively.

Hence, the value of n = [I(4-total e⁻s)I]; [I(6-total e⁻s)I] [I(8-total e⁻s)I] and [I(14-total e⁻s)I] respectively.

3.2. F-2 (For Set-2) - for the determination of number of unpaired electrons (n) of molecules or ions having total number of electrons (10-13) and (16-19) :

In this case, the number of unpaired electrons n = [I(PD-total e⁻s)I].

Here, PD = Penultimate electron digit (i.e. before last electron). e.g. for C₂⁻ (13e⁻s), the total number of electrons will be 13, PD = 12. Hence, unpaired electron n = I(12-total e⁻s)I = I(12-13)I = 1.

Hence, magnetic moment $\mu_s = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$ B.M. = $\sqrt{1(1+2)}$ B.M. = $\sqrt{3}$ B.M. = 1.73 B.M.

For F₂ (18e⁻s), the total number of electrons will be 18, PD = 18.

Hence, unpaired electron n = I(18-total e⁻s)I = I(18-18)I=0.

Hence, magnetic moment $\mu_s = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$ B.M. = $\sqrt{0(0+2)}$ B.M. = 0 B.M. = diamagnetic in nature.

3.3. F-3 (For Set-3) - for the determination of number of unpaired electrons (n) of molecules or ions having total number of electrons 20 :

In this case, the number of unpaired electrons n = [I(20-total e⁻s)I]. e.g. for Ne₂ (20e⁻s), the total number of electrons will be 20.

Hence, unpaired electron n = I(20-total e⁻s)I = I(20-20)I=0.

Hence, magnetic moment $\mu_s = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$ B.M. = $\sqrt{0(0+2)}$ B.M. = 0 B.M. = diamagnetic in nature.

Table 5. Magnetic moments of homo and hetero nuclear diatomic species

Species (Molecules or ions)	Total number of e ⁻ s	Number of unpaired electrons (n)	Magnetic moment (μ_s) in Bohr Magnetron (B.M.)	Remark on magnetic behavior
H ₂ ⁺	1	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
H ₂ , He ₂ ²⁺	2	0	0	Diamagnetic
H ₂ ⁻ , He ₂ ⁺	3	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
He ₂	4	0	0	Diamagnetic
Li ₂ ⁺ , He ₂ ⁻	5	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
Li ₂ , He ₂ ²⁻ , Be ₂ ²⁺	6	0	0	Diamagnetic
Be ₂ ⁺ , Li ₂ ⁻	7	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
Be ₂ , Li ₂ ²⁻	8	0	0	Diamagnetic
Be ₂ ⁻ , B ₂ ⁺	9	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
B ₂ , Be ₂ ²⁻ , HF	10	2	2.82	Paramagnetic
B ₂ ⁻ , C ₂ ⁺	11	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
C ₂ , B ₂ ²⁻ , N ₂ ²⁺ , CN ⁺	12	0	0	Diamagnetic
C ₂ ⁻ , N ₂ ⁺	13	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
N ₂ , CO, NO ⁺ , C ₂ ²⁺ , CN ⁻ , O ₂ ²⁺	14	0	0	Diamagnetic
N ₂ ⁻ , NO, O ₂ ⁺	15	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
NO ⁻ , O ₂	16	2	2.82	Paramagnetic
O ₂ ⁻	17	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
F ₂ , O ₂ ²⁻ , HCl	18	0	0	Diamagnetic
F ₂ ⁻	19	1	1.73	Paramagnetic
Ne ₂	20	0	0	Diamagnetic

4. New route for the evaluation of spin-multiplicity value :

Spin-multiplicity value and its corresponding spin state was first discovered by Friedrich Hund in 1925. The formula which is generally used for the prediction of spin-multiplicity value is $[(2S + 1)]$, where $S = \sum s =$ total spin quantum no.] is time consuming. To keep the matter in mind a simple innovative method has to be introduced for calculation of spin-multiplicity value and thus its corresponding spin state, shown in Table 6, in the easiest way by ignoring the calculation of total spin quantum number ($S = \sum s$).

First of all we should classify the species (atoms, molecules, ions or

Table 6. Spin-multiplicity value and its corresponding spin state

Spin-multiplicity value	Spin state
1	Singlet
2	Doublet
3	Triplet
4	Quartet
5	Quintet

complexes) for which spin-multiplicity value should be evaluated into three types based on the nature of alignment of unpaired electrons present in them.

4.1. Species having unpaired electrons in upward alignment (\uparrow) :

In this case, spin-multiplicity = $(n+1)$; where n = number of unpaired electrons.

Spin-multiplicity = $(n + 1) = (1 + 1) = 2$ (spin state = doublet); $(2 + 1) = 3$ (spin state = triplet) and $(3 + 1) = 4$ (spin state = quartet) respectively.

Spin-multiplicity = $(n + 1) = (2 + 1) = 3$ (in this case ignore paired electrons) (spin state = triplet) and $(1 + 1) = 2$ (spin state = doublet).

Spin-multiplicity = $(n + 1) = (0 + 1) = 1$ (spin state = singlet).

4.2. Species having unpaired electrons in downward alignment (\downarrow) :

In this case spin-multiplicity = $(-n+1)$

Here (-ve) indicate downward arrow.

Spin-multiplicity = $(-n + 1) = (-1 + 1) = 0$; $(-2 + 1) = -1$ and $(-3 + 1) = -2$ respectively.

Spin-multiplicity = $(-n + 1) = (-2 + 1) = -1$ (ignore paired electrons) and $(-1 + 1) = 0$ respectively.

4.3. Species having unpaired electrons in both mixed alignment (↑)(↓) :

In this case spin-multiplicity = $[(+n) + (-n) + 1]$

where, n = number of unpaired electrons in each alignment. Here, (+ve) sign and (-ve) sign indicate upward and downward alignment respectively.

Here total no. of unpaired electrons = 2 in which one having upward direction (+1) and other having downward mode (-1).

Hence Spin-multiplicity = $[(+n) + (-n) + 1] = [(+1) + (-1) + 1] = 1$ (spin state = singlet).

Here the total no. of unpaired electrons = 3 in which two unpaired electrons lie in upward (+2) and one unpaired electrons lie in downward (-1) .

Hence spin-multiplicity = $[(+n) + (-n) + 1] = [(+2) + (-1) + 1] = 2$ (spin state = doublet).

Here the total no. of unpaired electrons = 5 in which three unpaired electrons lie upward (+3) and two unpaired electrons lie downward (-2) .

Hence spin-multiplicity = $[(+n) + (-n) + 1] = [(+3) + (-2) + 1] = 2$ (spin state = doublet).

5. Identification of aromatic and anti-aromatic behaviour of organic compounds in aromaticity :

It was first devised by Hückel in 1931. The present study will be an innovative method involving two formulae by just manipulating the no. of π bonds within the ring system and delocalized electron pair (excluding π electron pair within the ring system) with one (01).

5.1. Prediction of aromatic behavior :

In the first case, the compound must be cyclic, planar (i.e. all the carbon atoms having same state of hybridization) with even number of A value, where $[A = \pi b + e^-p + 1$ (constant)], here πb = number of π bonds with in the ring system and e^-p = number of electron pair outside or adjacent to the ring system i.e. if the ring contains hetero atoms (atoms containing lone pair of electrons) which can undergo delocalization and each negative charge if present may be treated as one pair of electrons.

If the value of 'A', for a certain organic compound comes out as even number then this compound will be treated as aromatic compound.

5.2. Prediction of anti-aromatic behavior :

In the second case, the compound must be cyclic, planar (i.e. all the carbon atoms having same state of hybridization) with odd number of A value, where $[A = \pi b + e^-p + 1$ (constant)], here πb = number of π bonds with in the ring system and e^-p = number of electron pair outside or adjacent to the ring system i.e. if the ring contains hetero atoms which can undergo delocalization and each negative charge if present, may be treated as one pair of electrons.

If the value of 'A', for a certain organic compound comes out as odd number then this compound will treat as anti-aromatic compound.

5.3. General condition for non-aromatic behavior of organic compounds :

Any compound that lacks one or more of the above features i.e. it may be acyclic/non-planar, is to be treated as non-aromatic. But in this case, 'A' value may be even or odd number.

It is always to be noted that if the ring contains hetero atom like N, O, S etc., in this case we must count that electron pair in the evaluation of 'A' value which can undergo delocalization. We never count localized electron pair. Examples have been illustrated in Table 7.

There are some compounds which do not follow the above rule. Hückel's also cannot explain the aromatic or non-aromatic behavior of these compounds. These compounds have been represented in the Table 8.

If we easily predict the nature of organic compound i.e. aromatic, anti-

Table 7. Aromatic, anti-aromatic and non-aromatic behavior of organic compounds

Organic compound (cyclic, planar/cyclic, non-planar)	πb value [πb = number of π bonds with in the ring system]	e^-p value [e^-p = number of delocalized electron pair outside or adjacent to the ring system]	A value [$A = \pi b + e^-p +$ 1 (constants] (even no./odd no.)	Nature of compound (aromatic/anti- aromatic/non- aromatic)
Benzene or [6]annulene (cyclic, planar)	3π bonds	0	$3+0+1=4$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
Naphthalene (cyclic, planar)	5π bonds	0	$5+0+1=6$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
Anthracene (cyclic, planar)	7π bonds	0	$7+0+1=8$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
Cyclopropene (cyclic, non-planar due to one sp^3 hybridized carbon atom)	1π bond	0	$1+0+1=2$ (Even no.)	Non-aromatic
Cyclopropenyl cation (cyclic, planar)	1π bond	0	$1+0+1=2$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
Cyclopropenyl anion (cyclic, planar)	1π bond	1 (For one negative charge on carbon which undergoes delocalization)	$1+1+1=3$ (Odd no.)	Anti-aromatic
Cyclobutadiene or [4]annulene (cyclic, planar)	2π bonds	0	$2+0+1=3$ (Odd no.)	Anti-aromatic
Cyclopentadiene (cyclic, non-planar due to one sp^3 hybridised carbon atom)	2π bonds	0	$2+0+1=3$ (Odd no.)	Non-aromatic

Table 7 (contd.)

Cyclopentadienyl cation (cyclic, planar)	2π bonds	0	$2+0+1=3$ (Odd no.)	Anti-aromatic
Cyclopentadienyl anion (cyclic, planar)	2π bonds	1	$2+1+1=4$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
(For one negative charge on carbon which undergo delocalization)				
Cyclooctatetraene or [8] annulene (cyclic, planar)	4π bonds	0	$4+0+1=5$ (Odd no.)	Anti-aromatic
Cyclooctatrienyl cation (cyclic, non-planar due to one sp^3 hybridized carbon atom adjacent to positive charge)	3π bonds	0	$3+0+1=4$ (Even no.)	Non-aromatic
Pyridine (cyclic, planar)	3π bonds	0	$3+0+1=4$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
(Here lone pair on N does not take part in delocalization)				
Pyrrole	2π bonds	1	$2+1+1=4$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
(Here lone pair on N take part in delocalization)				
Furan	2π bonds	1	$2+1+1=4$ (Even no.)	Aromatic
(Here out of two lone pairs on O only one LP take part in delocalization)				

Table 8. Omission behavior of aromatic and non-aromatic organic compounds					
Organic compound (cyclic, planar/cyclic, non-planar)	π b value [π b = number of π bonds with in the ring system]	e^- p value [e^- p = number of delocalized electron pair outside or adjacent to the ring system]	A value [A = π b + e^- p + 1 (constant)]	Nature of compound	π b value [π b = number of π bonds with in the ring system]
	5 π bonds	0	5+0+1 = 6 (Even no.)	Non-aromatic	Due to the interaction of the hydrogen of 1 and 6 compound become non-planar
	8 π bonds	0	8+0+1=9 (Odd no.)	Aromatic	Because double bonded C ₁₅ C ₁₆ do not take part in resonance

aromatic or non-aromatic then we can resolve different kind of problems regarding stability, reactivity, acidity etc. by using the following supposition.

(1) Order of stability is aromatic > non-aromatic > anti-aromatic.

(2) Order of reactivity just follows the reverse order of stability as follows : anti-aromatic > non-aromatic > aromatic.

(3) Acidity : Stability of conjugate base s acidity.

e.g. cyclopentadienyl anion (aromatic) > cyclopentadiene (non-aromatic) > cyclopentadienyl cation (anti-aromatic). Hence, cyclopentadiene (its conjugate base i.e. cyclopentadienyl anion is aromatic in nature) is much more acidic than cycloheptatriene (its conjugate base i.e. cycloheptatrienyl anion is anti-aromatic in nature).

6. Calculation of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds in alkenes and cycloalkenes :

The molecular formula which defines a very large number of chemical structure, in this particular case, it is a herculean task to calculate the nature and number of bonds. Earlier Badertscher *et al.* studied a novel formalism to characterize the degree of unsaturation of organic molecules. But no such work has not been taken till now to calculate the number and types of bonds in open chain olefinic system having complex molecular formulae like $C_{176}H_{250}$, $C_{2000}H_{2000}$.

Keeping this in view, a rapid method has been proposed for the calculation of number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds with the help of following 06 (six) completely new formulae for certain aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

6.1. For open chain aliphatic hydrocarbons :

6.1.1. Calculation of π -bonds and double bonds (P) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in a given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing double bonds.

The formula to calculate the number of π bonds or double bonds for an aliphatic straight chain olefin is

$$P = [(2X - Y)/2] + 1$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and P = number of π bonds/double bonds.

e.g. : In $C_{176}H_{250}$, X = 176, Y = 250, therefore $P = (2 \times 176 - 250) / 2 + 1 = 51 + 1 = 52$ number of π -bonds or double bonds.

6.1.2. Calculation of σ -bonds (S) :

In this case, first we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing double bonds.

The formula to calculate the number of π bonds for an aliphatic straight chain olefin is

$$S = [X + Y - 1]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and S = number of sigma bonds (σ -bonds).

e.g. : In $C_{176}H_{250}$, X = 176, Y = 250, therefore $P = 176 + 250 - 1 = 425$ σ -bonds.

6.1.3. Calculation of single bonds (A) :

The total number of single bond for an aliphatic straight chain olefin is $A = [(3Y/2) - 2]$ where A = number of single bonds and Y is number of hydrogen atoms.

e.g. : In $C_{176}H_{250}$, Y = 250, therefore $A = [(3 \times 250 / 2) - 2] = 375 - 2 = 373$ single bonds. Examples have been illustrated in Table 9.

6.2. For cyclic aliphatic olefinic hydrocarbons :

6.2.1. Calculation of π -bonds and double bonds (P_c) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

The formula to calculate the number of π -bonds or double bonds for an aliphatic cyclic olefin is

$$P_c = [(2X - Y) / 2]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and P_c = number of π bonds or double bonds in the cyclic olefinic system.

e.g. : In cyclooctatetraene (C_8H_8), X = Y = 8, therefore $P_c = 16 - 8 / 2 = 4$ number of π bonds or double bonds.

Table 9. Calculation of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds in open chain olefinic hydrocarbons

Example (C_xH_y)	Straight-chain structure	π bond/ bonds [(2X-Y)/2+1]	σ bonds [X+Y-1]	Single bonds [(3Y/2)-2]	Double bond/bonds [(2X-Y)/2+1]
C_2H_4	$H_2C=CH_2$	1	5	4	1
C_3H_6	$H_2C=CH-CH_3$	1	8	7	1
C_3H_4	$H_2C=C=CH_2$	2	6	4	2
C_4H_8	(i) $H_2C=CH-CH_2-CH_3$ (ii) $H_3C-HC=CH-CH_3$	1	11	10	1
C_4H_6	(i) $H_2C=C=CH-CH_3$ (ii) $H_2C=CH-CH=CH_2$	2	9	7	2
C_4H_4	$H_2C=C=C=CH_2$	3	7	4	3
$C_{176}H_{250}$	-	52	425	373	52
$C_{2000}H_{2000}$	-	1001	3999	2998	1001
$C_{99}H_4$	-	98	102	4	98

6.2.2. Calculation of σ -bonds (S_c) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

The formula to calculate the number of σ bonds for an aliphatic cyclic olefin is

$$S_c = [X + Y]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and S_c = number of sigma bonds (σ -bonds) in cyclic olefinic system.

e.g. : In cyclooctatetraene (C_8H_8), X = Y = 8, therefore $S_c = 8 + 8 = 16$ number of σ bonds.

6.2.3. Calculation of single bonds (A_c) :

The total number of single bonds in aliphatic cyclic olefin can be calculated by using the formula $A_c = [3Y/2]$, where A_c = number of single bonds and Y is number of hydrogen atoms in aliphatic cyclic olefin.

e.g. : In cyclooctatetraene (C_8H_8), Y = 8, therefore $A_c = 24/2 = 12$ number of single bond. Examples have been illustrated in Table 10.

Table 10. Calculation of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds in cycloalkene system

Example (C _x H _y)	Cycloalkene	π bond/ bonds (P _c) = [(2X-Y)/2]	σ bonds (S _c) [X+Y]	Single bonds (A _c) [(3Y/2)]	Double bond/bonds [(2X-Y)/2]
C ₃ H ₄	Cyclopropene	1	7	6	1
C ₄ H ₄	Cyclobutadiene	2	8	6	2
C ₅ H ₆	Cyclopentadiene	2	11	9	2
C ₆ H ₈	Cyclohexadiene	2	14	12	2
C ₇ H ₈	Cycloheptatriene	3	15	12	3
C ₈ H ₈	Cyclooctatetraene	4	16	12	4

7. Calculation of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and triple bonds in alkyne and cycloalkyne :

The number and types of bonds in open chain and cycloalkynes having complex molecular formula is a Herculean task. Keeping this in view, a rapid method has been proposed for the calculation of number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and triple bonds with the help of following 08 (eight) completely new formulae by just manipulating the number of carbon and hydrogen atoms by using some factors for certain aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cycloalkynes.

7.1. Open chain aliphatic alkynes :

7.1.1. Calculation of π -bonds (P) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in a given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing triple bonds. The formula to calculate the number of π bonds for an aliphatic open chain alkyne, where there is one or more than one triple bonds is

$$P = [\{(2X-Y)/2\} + 1]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and P = number of π bonds.

e.g. : In C₁₆H₃₀, X = 16, Y = 30, therefore P = [\{(2X-Y)/2\} + 1] = [\{(2 \times 16 - 30)/2\} + 1] = 2 number of π bonds.

7.1.2. Calculation of σ -bonds (S) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and

the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in a given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing triple bonds. The formula to calculate the number of σ bonds for an aliphatic open chain alkyne, where there is one or more than one triple bonds is

$$S = [X + Y - 1]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and S = number of σ bonds.

e.g. : In $C_{16}H_{30}$, X = 16, Y = 30, therefore, $S = [X + Y - 1] = [16 + 30 - 1] = 45$ numbers of σ bonds.

7.1.3. Calculation of single bonds (A) :

The total number of single bond for an aliphatic open chain alkyne, where there is one or more than one triple bonds is

$$A = [\{(2X + 5Y)/2\} - 3]/2$$

where, A = number of single bonds, X = number of carbon atoms and Y = number of hydrogen atoms.

e.g. : In $C_{16}H_{30}$, X = 16, Y = 30, therefore, $A = [\{(2X + 5Y)/2\} - 3]/2 = [\{(2 \times 16 + 5 \times 30)/2\} - 3]/2 = [91 - 3]/2 = 44$ numbers of single bonds.

7.1.4. Calculation of triple bonds (T) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in a given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing triple bonds. The formula to calculate the number of triple bonds for an aliphatic open chain alkyne, where there is one or more than one triple bonds is $T = [\{(2X - Y)/2\} + 1]/2$, where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and T = number of triple bonds.

e.g. : In $C_{16}H_{30}$, X = 16, Y = 30, therefore, $T = [\{(2X - Y)/2\} + 1]/2 = [\{(2 \times 16 - 30)/2\} + 1]/2 = 2/2 = 1$ triple bond.

Examples have been illustrated in Table 11.

7.2. Cycloalkynes :

7.2.1. Calculation of π -bonds (P_c) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and

Table 11. Calculation of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds in open chain alkyne system

Example for open chain alkyne (C_xH_y)	π bonds [[{(2X-Y)/2}+1]	σ bonds [X+Y-1]	Single bonds [[{(2X+5Y)/2}-3]/2]	Triple bond/bonds [[{(2X-Y)/2}+1]/2]
$C_{10}H_{18}$	2	27	26	1
$C_{11}H_{20}$	2	30	29	1
$C_{12}H_{22}$	2	33	32	1
$C_{13}H_{24}$	2	36	35	1
$C_{14}H_{26}$	2	39	38	1
$C_{15}H_{28}$	2	42	41	1
$C_{16}H_{30}$	2	45	44	1
C_6H_6	4	11	9	2
$C_{12}H_{14}$	6	25	22	3

the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated cycloalkyne. The formula to calculate the number of π bonds for an aliphatic cycloalkyne is

$$P_c = [(2X - Y) / 2]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and P_c = number of π bonds in the cycloalkyne system.

e.g. : In cycloheptyne (C_7H_{10}), X = 7, Y = 10, therefore $P_c = (2 \times 7 - 10) / 2 = 2$ number of π bonds.

7.2.2. Calculation of σ -bonds (S_c) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated cycloalkyne. The formula to calculate the number of a bonds for an aliphatic cycloalkyne is

$$S_c = [X + Y]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and S_c = number of sigma bonds (σ -bonds) in cycloalkyne system.

e.g. : In cycloheptyne (C_7H_{10}), X = 7, Y = 10, therefore $S_c = (7 + 10) = 17$ number of σ bonds.

7.2.3. Calculation of single bonds (A_c) :

The total number of single bond for an aliphatic cycloalkyne is $A_c =$

$[\{(2X+5Y)/2\}]/2$; where, A_c = number of single bonds in cycloalkyne, X = number of carbon atoms and Y = number of hydrogen atoms.

e.g. : In cycloheptyne (C_7H_{10}), $X = 7$, $Y = 10$, therefore, $A_c = [\{(2X+5Y)/2\}]/2 = [(2 \times 7 + 5 \times 10)/2]/2 = 32/2 = 16$ numbers of single bonds.

7.2.4. Calculation of triple bonds (T_c) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in a given unsaturated cyclo system containing triple bond. The formula to calculate the number of triple bond is $T_c = [\{(2X-Y)/2\}]/2$, where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and T_c = number of triple bond.

e.g. : In cycloheptyne (C_7H_{10}), $X = 7$, $Y = 10$, therefore, $T_c = [\{(2X-Y)/2\}]/2 = [(2 \times 7 - 10)/2]/2 = 2/2 = 1$ triple bond.

Conclusions

It may be expected that these innovative methods would go a long way to help to the students of chemistry at Undergraduate, Senior Undergraduate and Post-Graduate level who would choose the subject as their career. Experiment *in vitro* on 100 students showed that by using these new innovative methods students can save up to 30–40 min time in the examination hall. On the basis of this, I can strongly recommend to use these new time economic interesting pedagogies.

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